

SOCIO-ECONOMIC ASPECTS OF WOMEN'S DOMESTIC SERVICE MIGRATION.

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Changes related to the transition to a market economy in Uzbekistan primarily affected labor relations. As a result, in the course of economic reforms, unemployment, which is an integral part of the economic system based on market relations, occurred. As a result of objective processes in the economy, thousands and millions of people lost their jobs and lost their source of income. In the newly independent young Republic, the system of professional education has not yet adapted to the system of training and retraining of qualified specialists based on the demands of the emerging market in the country. As a result, there was an imbalance between labor supply and demand in the labor market, which led to the formation of labor migration. The advantages of migration include finding a well-paid job, improving the quality of life, access to quality education and medical services, and broadening one's outlook on the spiritual side. However, migration is not without its negative aspects, such as the breakdown of families and the absence of family heads in the upbringing of children, the negative attitude of the local population to migrants, the lack of understanding of their customs, and the lack of stable living conditions are the disadvantages of migration. There can also be a lot of competition for jobs, and again, women who migrate will accept lower-paid jobs (albeit with higher education) to maintain their standard of living.

In addition, migration causes economic and political conflicts, and can affect the demographic situation in the countries where migrants go. According to sociologists, the biggest difficulty in migration is the local language and one of the biggest obstacles to migration.

Beneficial aspects fill vacancies, create competition among the labor force, increase business efficiency and accelerate economic growth. Migrant workers, regardless of their qualifications, also play a role in disseminating different cultures.

Women in domestic service have a high proportion of the elderly in the population, and in developed countries they are making cocktails. As young people are economically active in the population and move to large cities, care

for the elderly in the home service migration network is developing and benefiting society.

One of the positive aspects of migration is that in applying new ideas and skills, they bring knowledge and skills that are lacking in the local population, and are an additional source of tax for the receiving countries. Currently, some countries are faced with a demographic crisis, the native population is decreasing, the number of people capable of working is decreasing, and migrants are helping to fill their place.

According to the results of the survey, many companies prefer to hire foreign workers, because among the indigenous population, women who work in domestic service have families, are socially active and have daily tasks, which affects their work. Migrant women, on the other hand, are considered cheap laborers who can be away from their families and work full-time. According to demographer M.V Kurman, migration is a good option for filling the positions of workers.

Positive and negative aspects of women's domestic service cocktail migration Table 1

Migration subject	Positive aspects	The downsides
Migrant women working in domestic service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> increase in income; - improve the quality of life - possibility to buy items - knowledge and skills (language learning) - gain experience -having a child abroad using advanced techniques. - human rights and freedoms. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - psychological pressures; - women's distance from their children -socio-psychological consequences for families. - personal risks associated with movement - human traffickers or Victimization of exploiters the threat of being chi. Increasing family differences.
Host countries	- increase in supply in the labor market.	- the growth of unemployment;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -competition among manufactured products due to cheap labor -expansion of different culture - formation of scientific and technical potential - improvement of the demographic situation in the country 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Discriminatory actions or racism; - social instability - the risk of spreading dangerous diseases - culture and traditions national decline - the occurrence of conflicts between nations.
migrant exporting countries.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - money transfers - study effective ways of using labor - imported technologies - investment growth; - ensuring stability in the labor market 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> short scientific staff sh a negative impact on qualified specialists and production - emergence of demographic problems - loss of social status in families.

As can be seen in the table, the positive and negative aspects of migrant women and the country where they came to work were studied, but these factors may change depending on the country and the social background of the worker.

In order to regulate the labor migration of women's domestic service, under the direct leadership of the Ministry of "Employment and Labor Relations" of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to create a mechanism for hiring, training qualified workers and specialists in accordance with the orders of labor importing countries and large companies. In this, talented young people with professional qualifications and skills are selected on the basis of a competition, they are taught the language, history, customs, and traditions of the country where they have to work for a certain period of time, according to the chosen work, profession, craft. the necessary qualifications and skills are formed so that the migrant has the training to perform tasks at the level of the requirements of

the country or enterprise he is visiting. The establishment of labor force export on a scientific basis will greatly benefit the republic and:

- ✓ The amount of income from labor force export will increase sharply;
 - ✓ Young people are more interested in becoming a qualified worker or a qualified specialist, that is, in studying well;
 - ✓ The tendency and experience of young people to learn foreign languages increases;
 - ✓ Our young people, who have completed skilled work abroad, will have the opportunity to make a worthy contribution to the development of the national economy when they return to their country.

A number of data were analysed in the process of studying economic and social aspects of women's domestic service labor migration. According to the information of the Samarkand city justice court, in 2021, 1,680 applications for divorce were received. As evidence for divorce in court, families cited the following reasons: constant quarrels and disagreements in the family, differences in character, misunderstanding each other, infidelity, childlessness, and labor migration. This leads to an incomplete family life¹.

Reasons for divorce. Table 2

Disagreements in the family	38.7%
Differences in character	13.7%
Labor migration	13.2%
Violence	11.3%
Betrayal	8.3%
Childlessness	4.4%
Other reasons	10.3%

Today, many families in Uzbekistan participate in the migration. Also, divorces due to migration of women make up 13.2% of the total in the city of Samarkand alone, family betrayal due to women's migration occurs (8.3%), after family disagreements (38.7%) divorces due to migration are in the second place.

According to the data collected by the Institute of Macroeconomic and Territorial Studies, migration remains the main reason for divorce in some regions of our republic. There is a problem of disintegration and destruction of

¹<https://oxussociety.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/Domestic-Violence-Report-Oxus-Society-WC-Final.pdf> . Causes of divorce in Uzbekistan and domestic violence as a factor family troubles .

families due to labor migration. The loss of harmonious and effective relationships between parents and children causes a decrease in the quality of social and spiritual life. In the process of women's domestic service labor migration, various ailments may arise among migrants due to separation from their families and loved ones, missing their children, mental and physical stress. This situation harms their health.

Women are home The labor migration process is not always safe or fair. Women rely on jobs found through social media or by friends and relatives. Domestic service recruitment agencies have not yet been fully established in Uzbekistan. Therefore, they face the following problems:

- The legal status, functions, and liability measures of the active recruitment firms have not yet been fully defined. This causes problems in ensuring the rights and interests of workers .
- One of the urgent problems is the informal and uncontrolled nature of work in the field of domestic service. This leads to the weakness of mechanisms for protecting the rights and interests of workers.
- There are problems such as the fact that domestic service is one of the types of hard work, and the rights such as payment of wages, rest and movement are limited.
- false promises regarding employment, falsification of documents, terms and conditions of employment.
- There are various types of violence and harassment at the workplace, workers are not provided with legal assistance.
- wages and salaries. Or pay less than the agreed amount.
- Women working abroad are forced to work under any circumstances, otherwise they face visa problems.
- benefits of domestic workers .
- Non-availability of treatment, pregnancy and cocktail holidays.

Remittances coming to Uzbekistan due to migration, as targeted sources of household income, greatly contribute to family well-being and increase in living standards. They are a source of financing for basic human and real estate needs, which meet the educational, health and other needs of family members, while also providing economic growth.

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